

ANALYSIS THE SUBSYSTEM OF LABIAL PHONEMES OF THE KARAKALPAK LANGUAGE

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Abstract. This article is devoted to propose a scheme of a mandatory element of the model of the inventory system of phonemes, representing one genus-types level of phonemic relations: we can arrange the genus-types level in different ways. As an example, let's analyze the subsystem of labial phonemes of the Karakalpak language.

Keywords: language, labiality, Karakalpak, generic, analyze, integrator, connection, system, phonemes.

АНАЛИЗ ПОДСИСТЕМЫ ГУБНЫХ ФОНЕМ КАРАКАЛПАКСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена предложению схемы обязательного элемента модели инвентарной системы фонем, представляющей один родовидовый уровень фонематических отношений: мы можем расположить родовидовый уровень по-разному. В качестве примера проанализируем подсистему губных фонем каракалпакского языка.

Ключевые слова: язык, лабиальность, каракалпакский, родовой, анализ, интегратор, связь, система, фонемы.

Introduction

Generic relationship according to the integrator 'LABIALITY' [b] [p] [m] [w] [v] [f] – 'labial', 'erinlik', 'лабиальный'

- Specific connections by integrators 'tense', 'glide', 'fricative' or 'constrictive' and 'flat'
- Specific connection by integrator 'tense' [b], [p] +
- Specific connection by integrator 'glide' – [w]
- Specific connection by integrator 'constrictive' – 'саңлақлы', 'щелинный' – [v], [f] – ±
- Specific connection by integrator 'flat' – [m]

After determining the structure of one generic level, other generic levels should be established, covering the entire inventory of phonemes of this language.

How are the levels of genus-types relations located in the inventory system of phonemes? Let's consider this question on the example of a level that unites phonemes by the connection 'consonance', which reveals itself when the entire inventory of phonemes of a given language is considered, including both vowels and consonants

- first form subsystems of phonemes according to the type relationship 'vocality', and
- the second – according to the type relationship 'consonance'.

Consequently, the specific sublevel of the structure of the inventory system of phonemes of the language consists of opposed subsystems of vowels and consonants.

Now let's consider subsystems in which the number of phonemes is more than two, but less than the total number of phonemes in the **consonant** subsystem. The most numerous among the subsystems of the front-lingual phonemes in Karakalpak is the subsystem of the **Constrictive** or **Fricative** or **Spirant** – 7 phonemes, with which we will begin. In addition to the formation of a

gap for their articulation, the size of this gap in width is important: whether the stricture area forming the so-called areality is **narrow**, as in **whistling**, or **wide**, as in **sibilant**

From this point of view, the types subsystem of the **Spirants** coincides with the generic areal system of phonemes united by the sign of areality, which consists of the types subsystems of narrow-structured and wide-structured phonemes. Next comes the types subsystem of **fore-lingual** flat phonemes, coinciding with the generic subsystem that unites phonemes for which the **air duct** is important: whether it is oral or nasal.

Consequently, the specific subsystem of lingual **flat** phonemes coincides with the **air duct** generic system, which consists of the specific subsystems of orality and nasality.

When determining the location of subsystems, mini-systems and individual elements of the system in our model, it is important to note two points:

- First – only complete connections should be distinguished;
- Second – it is necessary to take into account both paired and group relationships of elements that are objectively present in reality.

The study of particular connections and oppositions between subsystems from broad to narrow and their distribution by structural genus-types levels is carried out by sequentially determining at each level the differentiator and its constituent oppositions, covering the largest number of phonemes of a given language, and integrators for subsystems of lower levels. Therefore, on the proposed universal scheme of the structure of the inventory phonological system of the language, we distinguish all structural levels, indicating generic integrators and types differentiators for each of them.

/.../ – the slash brackets denote the system,

/+/ – the private connection,

/–/ – the opposition,

/ :: / – the correlation relation.

The correlation relation is optional from the point of view that it can be replaced by a generic relationship;

- () – therefore it is given in brackets.
- /↓↑/ – the vertical arrows indicate the transition to the next hierarchical level;
- /→/ – the horizontal arrows indicate the ratio of the differentiator and its constituent opposites.

We present the proposed scheme as follows:

In terms of its conceptual content, the proposed scheme is somewhat different from those given by L.N. Cherkasov. In addition to the fact that the differentiators forming the structure are exclusively contrarian, in his works the system of consonant phonemes is analyzed in several stages –

- subsystems of labial,
- lingual advanced and
- lingual extended phonemes.

The results of the analysis are presented in the form of several diagrams that clearly display connections and oppositions, but not correlations, which are described separately [Cherkasov 19956: 285, 287, 290, 338, 340].

Conclusion

In our work, the structure is presented in its entirety, and the correlations are marked clearly, which greatly facilitates the perception of the overall picture of the result of the study of the relations of the inventory phonological system of the language.

REFERENCES

1. Abatbay Dauletov “Ha’zirgi qaraqalpaq tili. Fonetika”.No’kis,2005.
2. Баскаков Н.А “Введение в изучение тюркских языков”. 2-изд. Мб 1969.
3. Karl Heinrich Menges “Qaraqalpaq grammar”. King’s Crown Press, 1947.
4. Abdinazimov Sh, N, Pirniyazova A.Q, Shinnazarova S.J. “Ha’zirgi qaraqalpaq a’debiy tili . Fonetika, leksikologiya”. Tashkent, 2018.
5. Ганиева, М. ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ АБДУРАУФА ФИТРАТА. СЌЗ САНЪАТИ ЖУРНАЛИ JOURNAL OF WORD ART ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА, 12